

A Systematic Re-evaluation of the BEAVRS Benchmark with OpenMC

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ABSTRACT

There is a notable lack of easily reproducible, open-source, modern simulation benchmarks for nuclear reactors that can serve as credible references for verification and validation. To be effective, benchmarks should be supported by well-maintained models, comprehensive documentation, and clearly defined reference results to ensure long-term usability. In practice, however, this is rarely the case. The continual evolution of reactor physics simulation tools, including updates to geometry models, nuclear data libraries, and neutronics codes erodes the consistency and comparability of benchmark results over time.

This work presents a systematic re-evaluation of the BEAVRS Hot Zero Power benchmark, a widely used pressurized water reactor benchmark originally released in 2013. Using modern OpenMC versions, up-to-date cross section libraries, and refined modeling assumptions, the impact of a decade of changes can be quantified.

The goal of this paper is to resolve historical ambiguities in the benchmark specification, document the precise modeling assumptions and configurations used, and provide a transparent methodology for reproducing results across code versions and data libraries. The outcome is a robust, fully reproducible set of reference results for all Hot Zero Power configurations, generated using modern best practices in open-source modeling and data management.

Keywords: BEAVRS, OpenMC, Pressurized Water Reactor Benchmark, Monte Carlo, Full-Core Analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

The Benchmark for Evaluation and Validation of Reactor Simulations (BEAVRS) is a multi-cycle, full-core Pressurized Water Reactor (PWR) depletion benchmark developed by the MIT Computational Reactor Physics Group in 2013 [1]. Based on two operational cycles of a Westinghouse commercial nuclear power plant, BEAVRS has become a standard for the verification and validation of PWR simulations. At the time of the 2013 publication, simulations were performed using BEAVRS v1.0.1 and OpenMC v0.5.2 [2] to calculate the effective neutron multiplication factors (k_{eff}) and control rod worth values.

Since the original publication, this benchmark has been central to numerous published studies, confirming its value to the reactor physics community. A notable study used BEAVRS to investigate the effect of a windowed multipole cross section library on the k_{eff} . However, the k_{eff} results used as a baseline in this study differed from the original benchmark, likely due to the different run settings and expanded nuclide libraries used [3]. Others have used BEAVRS to verify novel methods, such as the cumulative migration method (CMM) for calculating neutron transport properties [4]. The benchmark has also been instrumental in validating a wide array of simulation codes, including DDC-3D [5], SuperMC [6], OpenMOC [7], SCALE/PARCS [8], DeCART/MATRA [9], MC21 [10], and OpenMC's own multi-group cross

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section generation capabilities [11].

The original BEAVRS publication highlighted a critical issue that persists today: most high-fidelity Monte Carlo nuclear benchmarks are proprietary, while the few open-source options often lack the detail required to validate modern simulation methods. However, since its initial release, both OpenMC and BEAVRS have undergone continuous development, now at versions 0.15.2 and 3.0.2 respectively. The changes made to BEAVRS over the past decade were necessary to maintain compatibility with new OpenMC releases and to improve the model's fidelity and usability. These significant software evolutions, coupled with the original analysis's reliance on deprecated software libraries, make an exact replication of the 2013 benchmark simulations nearly impossible. Therefore, an updated and reproducible set of benchmark values is needed for the BEAVRS benchmark at this point.

The goal of this work is to resolve historical ambiguities in the benchmark specification, document the precise modeling assumptions and configurations used, and provide a transparent methodology for reproducing results across modern code versions and data libraries all with open-source code. This is done by quantifying the impact of the evolution of both BEAVRS and OpenMC, performing analysis using all currently usable cross section libraries, analyzing the results different cross section temperature methods can cause, and clearly defining all components involved in the new benchmark results. This effort to provide a re-evaluation of the original BEAVRS benchmark will ensure its continued relevance and utility for the next generation of reactor physics analyses.

2. METHODOLOGY: DECONSTRUCTING BENCHMARK EVOLUTION

2.1 Computational Framework

The benchmark results presented in this paper are for the BEAVRS Cycle 1, Hot Zero Power (HZP) configuration. These conditions correspond to a core temperature of 566 K and a pressure of 15.5 MPa (560 °F and 2250 psia). The primary calculated quantity is the k_{eff} and control rod worths under various control rod bank configurations, calculated boron concentrations, and cross-section libraries.

Each simulation was done using 4,000,000 source particles per generation for 350 total batches, with the first 250 batches discarded as inactive to ensure source convergence. A fixed seed of 140211718 ("BEAVRS" in the A0Z25 cipher) was used for all calculations. While randomizing the seed for each run is preferable, a fixed seed was chosen in this work to guarantee that the results are precisely and easily reproducible.

All simulations, unless otherwise specified, were performed using OpenMC v0.15.2 and BEAVRS v3.0.2. Likewise, the default nuclear data library was ENDF/B-VII.1, processed from LANL ACE files available on the OpenMC data website, with adjustments made as described in section 2.3. The default OpenMC setting used for treating temperatures in between library temperatures was 'interpolation', which enables statistical interpolation between bounding temperatures in the loaded libraries to reduce bias.

2.2 Evolution of BEAVRS

To quantify the impact of the evolution of BEAVRS and OpenMC, a historical analysis was performed by running previous BEAVRS versions with their contemporary OpenMC releases using consistent baseline settings where possible.

Recreating historical results presented several technical challenges. BEAVRS versions 1.0.0-1.1.1 predate the modern OpenMC Python API, making performing simulations impractical. Furthermore, while versions 2.0.0 and 2.0.1 were released after the API's introduction, they were incompatible with the oldest OpenMC version readily available (0.9.0). Due to these constraints, simulations using these early code versions were not performed.

2.3 Nuclear Data and Temperature Libraries

OpenMC requires nuclear cross section data in a specific HDF5 format. The OpenMC project distributes several pre-generated libraries primarily derived from three sources: Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL) ACE files, Nuclear Energy Agency (NEA) ACE files, and raw ENDF data that were converted to ACE files. All these ACE files were then converted into HDF5 files by the OpenMC development team. Users can also generate custom libraries, which is particularly useful for creating Doppler broadened nuclear data at specific problem temperatures.

Although these libraries can be easily swapped when using OpenMC, there are minor inconsistencies between them that require preprocessing to ensure full compatibility. Specifically, libraries can often define elemental compositions in different ways depending on their origin, and newer libraries typically include larger sets of isotopic data. To run the simulations without changing the model, these missing data files had to be manually added to the libraries and declared in the cross-sections.xml configuration file. The specific nuclides missing from each evaluated library that are needed to run BEAVRS are summarized below:

- **LANL-derived Libraries:**
 - ENDF/B-VII.0: Required ^{12}C , ^{13}C , ^{18}O , ^{50}V , ^{51}V .
 - ENDF/B-VII.1: Required ^{12}C , ^{13}C , ^{18}O .
 - ENDF/B-VIII.0: Required **None**.
- **Raw Data Converted by OpenMC:**
 - ENDF/B-VII.1: Required ^{12}C , ^{13}C , ^{18}O .
 - ENDF/B-VIII.0: Required **None**.
- **NEA-derived Libraries:**
 - JEFF-3.2: Required ^{12}C , ^{50}V .
 - JEFF-3.3: Required ^{12}C , ^{112}Sn , ^{114}Sn , ^{115}Sn , ^{116}Sn , ^{117}Sn , ^{118}Sn , ^{119}Sn .

To ensure a consistent approach, all missing nuclide data were sourced from the LANL derived ENDF/B-VIII.0 library, except for ^{50}V needed in the NEA JEFF 3.2 library which was taken from the NEA JEFF 3.3 library. While the NEA JEFF 3.3 library does come with files for Sn isotopes, it has an error in its inelastic flag at 294 K at the time of this work. Consequently, these files were replaced to enable the library's use.

We also investigated the impact of the temperature settings for the chosen cross section library on the final k_{eff} value at a variety of temperatures. In modern OpenMC versions, users can specify how they want the code to handle intermediate temperatures not included in library data files. Two of the available methods to do this are by specifying 'nearest', where the program selects the data at the nearest temperature within the specified temperature tolerance, or 'interpolation' where the program calculates the interpolated values from the data below and above the specified operating temperature. We performed tests of both options using ENDF/B-VII.1 libraries from LANL at a variety of temperatures to observe the impact of these settings.

2.4 Validation Approach

This analysis aims to replicate the experimental Hot Zero Power (HZP) conditions, where the reactor is critical ($k_{\text{eff}} \approx 1$), using measured critical boron concentrations as a reference.

To isolate the effects of individual modeling choices, we modified a single benchmark parameter at a time, such as the cross section library or OpenMC version, while holding all else constant. This approach allows for the direct quantification of the impact of each parameter on k_{eff} and the predicted critical boron concentration, which clarifies the differences between the original 2013 benchmark and the present analysis.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: QUANTIFYING THE IMPACT OF CODE UPDATES

3.1 Evolution of BEAVRS

Table I shows the results of running the various versions of BEAVRS with the same settings and cross section libraries where possible. The original All Rods Out (ARO) HZP result from the 2013 benchmark (using BEAVRS v1.0.1) is included for comparison in the table as well for reference. The calculated k_{eff} for the same physical configuration can vary by more than 120 pcm depending on the software version used. This variance highlights the need to establish an updated, definitive baseline that accounts for the model's evolution over the years. For more information, a summary of major changes made to the BEAVRS model since its initial publication is provided in the accompanying GitHub repository.

Table I. Representation of how the evolution of BEAVRS over time has changed simulation results.

Date	BEAVRS Version	OpenMC Version	$k_{\text{eff}} \pm \sigma$
1/2/2025	3.0.2	0.15.2	0.99971 ± 0.00004
12/6/2020	3.0.1	0.12.0	0.99973 ± 0.00005
5/22/2018	3.0.0	0.10.0	1.00004 ± 0.00004
10/30/2017	2.0.2	0.9.0	1.00046 ± 0.00005
10/26/2016	2.0.1	0.8.0	-
9/6/2016	2.0.0	0.8.0	-
10/16/2013	1.1.1	0.5.2	-
2/21/2013	1.0.1	0.5.2	0.99920 ± 0.00004
1/31/2013	1.0.0	0.5.0	-

3.2 Verification of Modern OpenMC

To investigate the difficulty in recreating the original benchmark's k_{eff} values, a consistency check was performed across various OpenMC versions released since the 2013 publication [1]. This analysis was essential to determine whether the discrepancies in the results resulted from inconsistencies between different versions of the code.

The evaluation spanned from the oldest publicly available OpenMC version from Conda (0.9.0) to the most recent release at the time of this work (0.15.2), with tests conducted on each major intermediate version. Table II presents the results of the execution of an identical BEAVRS model with each OpenMC version tested. Notably, a different cross section library format was required for versions 0.9.0 and 0.10.0 due to a change in the HDF5 file structure that was introduced in OpenMC version 0.11.0. The cross section library used for these versions was also ENDF/B-VII.1. Creating the library manually from ENDF

files, however, could have caused the slight discrepancy observed between the results from these versions and all subsequent versions.

*Table II. OpenMC version consistency test.**

OpenMC Version	$k_{\text{eff}} \pm \sigma$
0.15.2	0.99971 ± 0.00004
0.15.0	0.99971 ± 0.00004
0.14.0	0.99971 ± 0.00004
0.13.0	0.99972 ± 0.00004
0.12.0	0.99968 ± 0.00004
0.11.0	0.99977 ± 0.00004
0.10.0	0.99989 ± 0.00005
0.9.0	1.00001 ± 0.00004

**The same materials, geometry, and settings XML files from BEAVRS version 3.0.2 were used for all tests in Table II.*

3.3 Impact of Cross Section Library Selection

Table III shows the results of using all nuclear data libraries described in section 2.3 using identical simulation parameters and settings. The LANL ENDF/B-VII.1 library was chosen to be the baseline for consistency with the 2013 BEAVRS benchmark.

Tests were also performed with and without thermal scattering enabled for H in H₂O to evaluate the effect of this setting on k_{eff} . In each case, enabling thermal scattering increased the k_{eff} by less than 80 pcm. These results align with similar studies done involving BEAVRS [11], where differences in k_{eff} of approximately 100 pcm were observed. Small changes in k_{eff} are observed because its gradient with respect to temperature at 566K is significantly smaller than at 300K as was done in [11].

Table III. Consistent simulation runs with different cross section libraries. Baseline library highlighted.

Raw Data Source	ACE Library Source	$k_{\text{eff}} \pm \sigma$ with Thermal Scattering Library	$k_{\text{eff}} \pm \sigma$ without Thermal Scattering Library
ENDF/B-VII.0	LANL	1.00008 ± 0.00005	0.99981 ± 0.00004
ENDF/B-VII.1	LANL	0.99971 ± 0.00004	0.99962 ± 0.00005
ENDF/B-VII.1	NJOY 2016.68	1.00015 ± 0.00004	0.99947 ± 0.00004
ENDF/B-VIII.0	LANL	1.00129 ± 0.00005	1.00123 ± 0.00005
ENDF/B-VIII.0	NJOY 2016.68	1.00123 ± 0.00004	1.00121 ± 0.00004
JEFF 3.2	NEA	0.99927 ± 0.00005	0.99848 ± 0.00004
JEFF 3.3	NEA	1.00362 ± 0.00004	1.00335 ± 0.00004
JEFF 3.3	NJOY 2016.68	1.00405 ± 0.00004	1.00330 ± 0.00005

Tests could not be performed using the FENDL 3.2 from the IAEA NDS ACE files. The FENDL 3.2 library was unusable as its single-temperature data (293 K) are incompatible with the required temperature interpolation for the 566 K operating conditions.

3.4 Impact of Temperature Treatment

Figure I shows the results of testing the temperature methods 'interpolation' and 'nearest' when using the LANL derived ENDF/B VII.1 cross section library at a variety of temperatures. These results suggest that using the temperature method of 'interpolation' achieves a k_{eff} value closer to unity than using 'nearest' does at the operating temperature of BEAVRS, leading to the decision to use the 'interpolation' temperature method in the final benchmark specifications. The change in the gradient of the k_{eff} versus temperature curve when the 'nearest' temperature method is used is due to intermediate temperatures in $S(\alpha,\beta)$ libraries being available.

Figure I. Impact on k_{eff} at variety of temperatures using temperature methods "interpolation" and "nearest".

3.5 Synthesis and New Reference Results

Using the framework outlined in Section 2.1, definitive values for k_{eff} and control rod bank worths were calculated for all HZP configurations during Cycle 1 of the BEAVRS reactor, with the results presented in Table IV. The sum of the absolute differences between the calculated and measured bank worths is now 170 pcm, a notable reduction from the 234 pcm deviation reported in the original benchmark.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a high-fidelity, comprehensive re-evaluation of the BEAVRS benchmark, establishing an updated and more reliable set of reference results for the Cycle 1 HZP conditions. This work was necessitated by significant evolution in both the BEAVRS model and the OpenMC code since the benchmark's original publication. Through a systematic analysis, this study quantified the impact of model updates, verified the consistency of OpenMC across major versions, and demonstrated the influence of nuclear data library selection on simulation outcomes. The resulting configuration significantly improves the agreement with experimental control rod worths, establishing new, high-fidelity reference for the validation and verification of modern reactor physics codes.

The establishment of this robust HZP baseline provides a strong foundation for future research. Key areas for future work include extending the benchmark to include Cycle 2 depletion data, performing detailed burnup calculations, and determining benchmark multigroup diffusion parameters.

The results presented herein are intended to serve as the new definitive Cycle 1 HZP reference for the BEAVRS benchmark. All model specifications and detailed data are publicly available from the MIT Computational Reactor Physics Group (<https://crpg.mit.edu/>), and all code used for these benchmark results can be found on the GitHub (<https://github.com/baileyoteri/BEAVRS-2026-Cycle-1-HZP-Benchmark>).

Table IV. Results from BEAVRS v3.0.2 using OpenMC v0.15.2 code for HZP conditions for Cycle 1 of the benchmark specifications.

OpenMC Results			
HZP Critical Boron Evaluation	Tallied $k_{eff} \pm \sigma$	Boron Concentration [ppm]	Δ from ARO k_{eff} [pcm]
ARO	0.99971 \pm 0.00004	975	-
D in	1.00129 \pm 0.00004	902	158
C, D in	1.00045 \pm 0.00004	810	74
A, B, C, D in	0.99871 \pm 0.00004	686	-100
A, B, C, D, SE, SD, SC in	0.99717 \pm 0.00005	508	-255

HZP Bank Worths	Tallied $(k_1 - k_0)/(k_1 k_0) * [pcm]$	Measured [pcm]	Difference [pcm]
D	777 \pm 7	788	-11
C with D in	1245 \pm 6	1203	42
B with D, C in	1214 \pm 7	1171	43
+A with D, C, B in	552 \pm 7	548	4
SE with D, C, B, A in	487 \pm 7	471	16
+SD with D, C, B, A, SE in	802 \pm 7	772	30
+SC with D, C, B, A, SE, SD in	1123 \pm 7	1099	24

* k_0 and k_1 are the OpenMC k_{eff} values before and after insertion of the bank, at the critical boron concentration of each rod-withdrawn configuration.

† Where no boron data were provided for the rod-withdrawn configuration, k_0 and k_1 were found using a boron concentration extrapolated from the existing data uniformly with original benchmark from 2013 [1].

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